

An etymological feast: New work on most of the PIE roots beginning with **ste-*, including a new etymology for PIE **(s)teg-*, “to cover”; a new etymology for Latin *sturnus* (=“starling”) and Middle English *staer* (“starling”) and Old Prussian *starnite* (“gull”); new etymologies for Ancient Greek *basileus*, *stokhos* and *petra*; new work continuing my work on PIE **h₂eyǵ-* (“goat”), **h₂eyǵ-* (oak tree), now likely encompassing also PIE **h₂enǵ^h-*, */*h₂emǵ^h-*, “tight, narrow”; a new etymology for Latvian *ozols* (oak tree), Old Prussian *anzonis*, and their immediate cognates; new work on PIE **kel-*, “to cover”, PIE **kel-*, “thin shaft, stalk”, PIE **kelh₂*, “to prick, sting, stab”, PIE **kolm-* “reed, cane, straw”, Etruscan *Cel* (earth goddess), Ancient Greek *selinon* (celery); PIE **kerd-*, “heart”; a new etymology for Latin *cattus* (“cat”), a new etymology for Spartacus (=strong, firm) and explaining why the *spara-takos* etymology from decades ago is wrong; a new etymology for Minoan Knossos (=Fortress), Minoan/Linear A *Po-to*=“big, grand”, the Proto-Germanic word for “silver” and many more new etymologies

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Introduction

This is the first draft of a work (much abbreviated because there is so much I wanted to publish in a timelier manner) that I will augment in the near future. This work deals with many new etymologies, with many PIE roots and with many words in a number of IE languages: the unifying theme is roots that meant “stiff; erect; to project; pointed, sharp, to cut” (and I will explain the various meanings and why they pertain to such a set in these cases), but I will include some other kinds of work in this paper as well, proceeding from that unifying theme. He or she who is able to read this entire work will be rewarded with much new factual knowledge, I can guarantee.

1.

I posit that the PIE roots **steh*₂- “to stand (up)”, **steyh*₂- , “to stiffen”, **steb*^h- , “to stand still; harden”; **steg*^h- “to project vertically”, **(s)teg*-, “to project vertically”, **(s)teyg*- “to be sharp, to sting”, **steyg*^h-, “to go; to climb”; **(s)teg*-, “to cover”, **steyp*-, “be stiff, erect”, **streyg*-, “line, stroke; shear”, **sterh*₃-/**ster*- “to stretch, to expand, spread”; PIE **sterh*₃, “to be stiff”; PIE **streng*^h- “to twist, rope, cord”, PIE **steg*^{wh}- “to enlace”, PIE **stel*- , “to be stiff>to put, to set in place, to place”; PIE **steng*^w- “to push”, PIE **sterb*^h- “to become stiff; to tighten the muscles¹>to exert (force, work), PIE **(s)telH*-“to be still>to be silent”; are all cognate: they all come from the same sonic-semantic reflex in one group of ancient speakers, where **ste*- denoted “stiff and somewhat narrow, projecting; pointed”.

The idea of “projecting” obviously involves/includes “projecting vertically/to project vertically” and also “projecting horizontally/to project horizontally”, and from “projecting horizontally/to project horizontally” I argue developed “stretching; to stretch”---and then the “narrow” connotation (which most likely was present at that time) was dropped in order to create the meanings “to spread” which I argue led to “to cover”, found in PIE **(s)teg*-“to cover; roof”².

The meanings “make stiff, tight” led to “that with which one brings together things in a tight bundle; that with which one tightens something”, which led to “rope, cord, to twist (in order to tighten)”--->PIE **streng*^h- “to twist, rope, cord”, and the meanings “make stiff, tight” led to “to tighten with a cord, vine, rope; to enlace, wrap around”-- → PIE **steg*^{wh}- “to enlace³, wrap around” (source of Proto-Hellenic **sték*^{whō}⁴, source of Ancient Greek στέφω, “I wreath, garland>I encircle, crown, I put around”).

The meanings “to project horizontally, to project vertically; line” I argue led to PIE **steyg*^h- “to go” and “to walk” and “to climb” (for more about the semantic development “to go” from “a line”, see Old English *strīcan*=“to go, move, proceed” and also “to pass lightly over, to stroke, smooth, rub”: Old English *strīcan* derives from PIE **streyg* (“line, stroke”), a root which is cognate to PIE **steyg*^h- “to go; to climb”).

1 The source I referenced posits that PIE **sterb*^h- meant “to become stiff” and also “to exert (force, work)”: here I argue that the meanings “to exert force, to work” come from “to tighten the muscles”, from “to become stiff”.

2 An alternative theory would be that PIE **(s)teg*-, “to cover” developed from the earlier meaning **(s)teg*=“straw, reeds, twigs, branches” used as thatch for thatched roofs, and **(s)teg*=“wood beams” used to make roofs. Or **(s)teg*- referring to the peak of a roof, to the fact that the roof is on top, elevated, with **(s)teg*=“rising, pole; peak; top; elevated; a pile”. I posited and published all those theories in two Academia.edu Sessions in September and October 2022.

3 See Old French *enlacer*=“to wrap around”, etc.

4 Beekes, Robert S. P. (2010) *Etymological Dictionary of Greek* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 10), with the assistance of Lucien van Beek, Leiden, Boston: Brill.

PIE *stew-, “to praise, laud” I argue comes from “to elevate” which came from “to rise/project vertically”: for a parallel example in PIE, see PIE *g^werH- which meant “to elevate” as well as “to praise>express approval”.

The meanings “something projecting; pointed; stiff; hard” led to “to push, hit”, seen in PIE *steng^w- “to push”, PIE *(s)tew-, “to push, hit”, PIE *(s)tewg-, “to push, hit”, PIE *(s)tewk- “to push, press; to strike, beat; to stick into, pierce, perforate”; PIE *(s)tewp- “to push, to stick”. Something soft cannot really hit or strike or push, so those meanings come from “hard, firm, stiff” as well as sometimes from “pointed”, while “to stick” is from “pointed” as well as “firm”, as suggested by the penis, by sticking in a stick (note how “stick” and “sticking” are cognate), etc.

PIE *(s)teh₂y- “to steal” is also the source of words meaning “to hide, conceal” (see Proto-Slavic *tajiti=“to hide, conceal”) and “secrecy; mystery” (see Proto-Slavic *tajъna=secrecy, mystery): looking at the other words derived from this root, I posit that PIE *(s)teh₂y- could have come from a lost pre-PIE *(s)teh₂y- =“to cover”, from earlier “to spread<stretch<project horizontally”: unless, also perhaps possible, the meaning “to steal” came from “to strike, hit”, from “pointed; projecting” (rather than the meanings “to hit, strike” developing from “to stroke, to pass lightly over/touch with a linear movement”: see the next paragraph for such semantic developments in other words).

With PIE *streyg-, we see some other semantic developments coming from “line, stroke (as in a line)”: we find “stroke (as in a linear movement)” led to “to stroke as in to touch across something/someone in a linear movement>to touch lightly/pass lightly over, to smooth, to rub; to paint, to smear”, and on the other hand to “to shear; cut hair”. The meaning “to strike” seen in English “strike” is already determined to have developed from “to stroke, to touch with a movement passing across something/someone”, as seen by the meanings of Old English *strīcan* (see above). Also cognate is PIE *strewg^h-, the source of Proto-Germanic *streukaną, “to stroke, wipe” and Proto-Germanic *strukkōną, “to stroke, sweep”.

PIE *steyh₂- “to stiffen” led to some words meaning “stone, rock, pebble”, including Ancient Greek *στία* (“pebble”), *στῖον* (“small stone; pebble”), Proto-Slavic *stěna “rock, lump; stone wall>wall; cliff”; Proto-Germanic *stainaz (“stone”). It may be that Ancient Greek *πέτρᾱ* (“rock formation; cliff, ledge, ave, ridge; stone (building material)”) comes from a *k^wet- that meant “stiff” which was part of a semantic set “stiff; to project up stiff; pointed” and other related meanings.

Ancient Greek *βᾶσιλεύς* (“chief; master; king; lord; patron”), thought to derive from an earlier *g^watiléus (based on Mycenaean Greek *g^wasiléus*, and other considerations), may come from 1) a *g^wat= “strong<stiff”; or 2) *g^watiléus may

come from “lofty/high (in the figurative sense)” from *g^{wat}=”to project vertically; stiff”; or *g^{wat}iléus may come from (as I first argued in my work on the Kjolmen inscription in early March 2022) *g^{wat}=”to strike, hit” from earlier *g^{wat}=”pointed; projecting (leading to “to strike”); a line; to stroke (with “to stroke” leading to “to strike” as seen in English)”: all these *g^{wat} options that I describe would likely be akin to/would likely derive from (via unknown Pre-Greek languages) an earlier *k^{wet}=”stiff”.

Ancient Greek σθένος (“strength, might, power”) most likely comes from this PIE and Pre-PIE *ste- meaning “stiff”, via one of the many root-words that are part of this set (as I also argued before in my work on the Thracian Ezerovo ring inscription) or via an unattested variant from this set. Due to the strong showing of such forms in Indo-European languages, I expect that the -steneas in the Thracian name Rolisteneas (which may be found on the ring, but the ring has no word breaks so it is disputed whether the ring contains the name Rolisteneas or Rolistene, or even any whether it contains any form representing a word from a *ste root, if one argues for a Rolis/tene parsing...which I find unlikely) is a native Thracian form (not a borrowing from Ancient Greek), most likely meaning “strong, firm”. Compare the meanings of Middle English stith: “stiff, steady, stable, not pliable; strong, brave (not fleeing, keeping steady, firm), having strength; mighty; the meaning stiff also leading to inflexible, cruel, severe, intense. Middle English stith derives from Proto-Germanic *stinþaz (=stinthaz).

Ancient Greek στόχος had the attested meanings: 1) pillar of brick; 2) synonym of στοχάς, which meant “an erection of stone or wood for fixing net poles”; 3) target; 4) aim, aiming; 5) guess, conjecture---I posit that the meaning “target” came from posts/something immobile and rising being used as targets, with “post/something immobile and rising” deriving from “to project vertically; be stiff”, and the meanings “aim, aiming” developed from “target” and the meanings “guess, conjecture” derive from “shooting a guess, conjecture, like trying to hit a target”. Also possible is that the meaning “to project horizontally” led to “to send something at a target; to aim; guess, conjecture”, but I prefer the scenario that theorizes that posts--or at least something immobile and rising--were used as targets.

I will publish here my theory that Latin *sturnus* (starling), the *star-* in English *starling*, Middle English *stær* (=starling), Old Prussian *starnite* (gull) derive from an earlier meaning of “stiff/harsh voice”, referring to the voices of starlings and gulls. The harsh voices of starlings are one of their most remarkable characteristics, making them be (along with other reasons) unwanted birds in many peoples’ backyard or frontyard. My theory matches the evidence (see how Old English *stær*, “starling” derives from a Proto-Germanic form *staraz, and

*staraz also meant “stiff” in Proto-Germanic: but the bird does not have stiff movements; see how *stær* in Old English also meant “stare”, as in “to stare”, deriving from **ster-*, “to be stiff”) and matches the usual Slavic names for such birds: see Proto-Slavic **skvorьсь* (=“starling”) which comes from *skvьрь-* “scream”, per Vasmer et al. There’s no indication that the starling words beginning with “*st-*” (*sturnus*, *staer*, etc.) derive from “iridescent”, “spotted”, “dark”, “flocking” (referring to the often very large flocks of starlings), “to peck”---the evidence points to their voices. Nor do I know of anyone arguing that they derive from iridescent, spotted, dark or flocking.

2.

I compare Basque *astigar/azkar* (both forms in use: they both mean “maple tree”) to Romanian *stejar* which means “oak tree” and Bulgarian *стежер* (= *stežer*, “pole” and also has the meaning “oak tree” in some Bulgarian dialects) and dialectical Bulgarian *стеж* (= *stež* = *Quercus pubescens*, known as “white oak” in English), alternative form *стежяк* (*stežjak*). The Romanian and Bulgarian words derive from a root **steg* or **steg^{h-}* which had the meaning “stiff, erect, narrow, tight, strong, somewhat narrow and projecting/long, long and pointed, pointed, sharp (because that which is pointed is always projecting, and that which is sharp is usually made of stiff/hard material)”, referring primarily to the trunk of the oak trees but possibly also to the penis-like and pointed acorns. Since Bulgarian *стеж/стежяк* is dialectical, and since the meaning “oak tree” for *стежер* is dialectical, and since there are apparently no such oak tree words in other Slavic languages, the Romanian and Bulgarian words are likely from Daco-Thracian, with Slavic cognates and with cognates in other IE languages as well, all deriving from PIE **steg* or **steg^{h-}*.

I argue that Basque *astigar/azkar* derive from a root similar and akin and maybe even identical to the **steg* or **steg^{h-}* roots described above, and so the words *astigar/azkar* refer to the pole/trunk of the maple trees and/or to the pointed leaves.

While Basque *ezkur* (“acorn”), which is so similar to *azkur* (maple tree), derives from a root that had the same semantic range/same meanings as **steg/ste^{h-}*, but formally (in terms of form) the root of *ezkur* may have been more like or identical to PIE **h₂eyǵ-* / **h₂eǵ-*.

Now compare **h₂eǵ-* to **steg-*, and PIE **h₂eyǵ-* to PIE *(*s*)*teyg-* “to prick, stab, sting”, and to PIE **steyg^{h-}* “to go”, “to walk”, “to climb”: the forms beginning with **st-* and the forms beginning with **h₂₋* I think are autonomous (one does not derive from the other by sound-shift), but they are chiming forms which came

from kindred sonic/verbal/locutionary-semantic reflexes in a group of speakers and the roots underwent similar/parallel developments.

Basque *ezkur* (=acorn) is already thought (cf. Kroonen 2013) to likely be cognate to Latin *aesculus* (=the winter oak or Italian oak: the Italian oak has acorns which are very edible/comestible for humans) and already thought to likely also be cognate to PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree” (cf. Kroonen, 2013): Latin *aesculus* is likely from an earlier **aig-sculus*; it is less likely for *aesculus* to be unrelated to PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree”, and so it’s less likely that Basque *ezkur* is cognate with Latin *aesculus* but not with PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree”: it’s more likely that *ezkur* is cognate with both *aesculus* and PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree”.

In earlier works of mine, I already posited that PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree” comes from **h₂eyǵ-* referring either to the rising pole of the oak tree or to the pointed, penis-like acorns (for this option, compare Latin *glans*=acorn and penis, and Ancient Greek *balanos*=acorn and penis) or both options at the same time. And I posited that PIE **h₂eyǵ-/h₂eǵ-* (“goat”) was a reference to the long-penises of males goats and a reference to their lasciviousness; the sprouting rising horns; the long pointed teats on the udders of female goats; and likely also a reference to climbing mountains, climbing hills/cliffs and mounting females: for the climbing/mounting option/connotation, compare PIE **h₂eyǵ-* (goat) and PIE **steyǵh-* “to climb”.

A variant of **h₂eyǵ-* (goat) is PIE **h₂eǵ-* (goat), and I see a possible link between **h₂eǵ-* (goat<penis; pole<to be stiff and erect) and PIE **h₂enǵh-/h₂emǵh⁵*, ”tight, narrow”. I posit that PIE **h₂enǵh-/h₂emǵh-*, “tight, narrow” comes from an earlier fuller set of meanings: “stiff, erect; tight, narrow; pointed, sharp; projecting”, and also “strong” and so on (see the discussion of the *ste-* forms above).

If PIE **h₂eǵ-* (goat) and hypothetical **h₂eǵ-* (“oak tree”; which I posit as a likely variant form of PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =oak tree) and PIE **h₂eyǵ-* =”oak tree” have the same origin as **h₂enǵh-/h₂emǵh-*, ”tight, narrow”, it would provide a great explanation for Latvian *ozols*=oak tree, Samogitan *ōžouls*, Lithuanian *q̄žuolas*, *ažuolis* (i-stem), *aržuolas* (which may be a rhoticisim from earlier unattested **anžuolas*), *ūžuolas* (compare Old East Slavic *uzūľ*, from earlier Proto-Slavic **q̄zlь*, “knot”, from PIE **h₂enǵh-/h₂emǵh-*, ”tight, narrow”), *vúožuolas* (compare Ukrainian *vúzol* from Proto-Slavic **q̄zlь*, “knot”) and Old Prussian *ansonis* (*anzōnis*), all of disputed etymology.

The etymology of the variant *ážuolas* is more difficult, but I expect that the initial *á-* is from a blending of *ūžuolas* and *q̄žuolas*: in any case, the variant

⁵ **h₂emǵh-* according to Kroonen, Guus, (2013) *Etymological Dictionary of Proto-Germanic* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 11).

áužuolas can probably be explained as a later development, without invoking an old variant of PIE **h₂eǵ^h-/*h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*. While *aržuolas* may be from a root that is also the source of Proto-Slavic **verzti*, “to tie, to squeeze”, rather than rhoticism from **anžuolas*: this root, the source of **verzti*, would have had the older meanings “stiff, tight, strong, erect”, etc.

So in my scenario, Latvian *ozols*, Samogitan *ōžouls*, Old Prussian *anzōnis* and Lithuanian *ąžuolas*, *ažuolis* (i-stem), *ūžuolas*, *vúožuolas*, *aržuolas* (if rhoticised from *anž-*) derive not exactly from **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*, =”tight, narrow”, but instead from the earlier **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*, =”pole; stiff; erect; tight; narrow”: so those Baltic oak tree words are not a reference to “knotty>twisted”⁶ (which would be referring to the branches and to the trunks) but instead to the stiff, firm pole of the oak tree, since probably most oak trees have high straight trunks rather than bent/curving trunks.

My theory that there was a root **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*, =”pole; stiff; erect; tight; narrow” may seem strange at first sight to some people, until they realize that PIE **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*, “tight, narrow” is already thought to likely be akin to PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp” and therefore to PIE **h₂eyk-* (“to sting; sharp tip, barb”) as well---things that are sharp are also stiff, of compressed/dense material, usually of strong material, such as sharpened stone, metal, hard wood etc.---so that’s why we find these semantic links and semantic progressions (plus the penis is tubular, pointed, and gets stiff, hard, erect, and that was a big part of the semantic set coalescing as it did), seen in examples such as PIE **steg^h-/*steng^h-* “to sting; rod, blade; sharp, stiff”. And note the parallel development, the parallel nasalization: **steg^h-/*steng^h-* vis-a-vis **h₂eǵ^h-/*h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*.

The dialectical Lithuanian form *aižuols* (“oak tree”) is agreed to derive from PIE **h₂eyǵ-*, “oak tree” (for example, Kroonen’s 2013 work derives *aižuols* from **aiǵ-ōl*, in turn from PIE **h₂eyǵ-*, “oak tree”). But the etymology of the “standard” Lithuanian form *ąžuolas* is disputed: some argue that it derives, via intermediary steps, from *aižuols*; others believe that it is not likely to derive from *aižuols*, and instead derives from a form beginning with *(h)anž-*, in turn from **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*: my theory considers **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-* to be variants of a slightly (?) earlier **h₂eǵ^(h)-/*h₂eǵ-*, which was paired with a **h₂eyǵ-* form.

Up until this paper was published, PIE **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-* and PIE **h₂eyǵ-*, “oak tree” were assumed to be unrelated. Working from that assumption that no one thought to challenge, it was argued that Lithuanian *ąžuolas*, Latvian *ozols*, Old Prussian *anzonis* (et al.) derive from the meaning “twisted, gnarled”, from the earlier meanings “knotty”/“knotted”<“knot”<“tight”, from PIE **h₂enǵ^h-/*h₂emǵ^h-*, and cognate to Proto-Slavic **(v)qzlъ* 'knot' a. p. a (a. p. a

6 As posited by someone/several someones before this work of mine.

points to the Balto-Slavic acute)⁷, Proto-Slavic **vĕzàti* “to tie”⁸: but I prefer my theory, that those Baltic oak tree words do not derive from the idea/meaning “gnarled, twisted, knotty” but instead from “stiff, firm pole” and from “pointed acorns”.

Besides PIE **h₂enǵʰ-/*h₂emǵʰ-*, there is also thought to be a PIE **h₂eng-* “to curve, bend”. But the meaning “curve” for the PIE root **h₂eng-* “to curve, bend” is weakly attested because most of the words thought to derive from this root can be explained as deriving instead from “pointed; stiff”: Tocharian A *ānkar* “tusk (of an elephant)”, Tocharian B *āñkār*, “tusk (of an elephant)”, Ancient Greek ἄγκυρα (“anchor”, “hook”), ἄγκος (the “bend” meaning is explained well as coming from “point of an angle, point of a corner”, while the meanings “mountain glen, dale, valley” could have arisen from from the same “point of an angle, point of a corner” or from “that which is hollowed out by something pointed/sharp”, or could have arisen from a blend of both), Proto-Germanic **ankulaz*, “ankle, hip”: both “ankle” and “hip” could be from “point of angle, point of a corner”, or from “pointed” leading to “to affix (by thrusting in a nail, like in a yoke for oxen) one thing to another, to join (by thrusting in a nail)”; Ancient Greek ἄγγος/*ángos* (=bowl, vat, pitcher, coffin, casket, womb, stomach, cell of a honey-comb, etc.) likely derives from the meaning “hollowed out by something sharp/pointed” (as seen with most of the Ancient Greek words for “hollow; abdomen; belly; loins; flank” and as seen in the etymologies of various bowl words in various languages), in turn from **h₂eng-* “sharp, pointed, stiff, tight, strong” and so on.

So when I say the Baltic oak tree words more likely do not derive from “gnarled, twisted, knotty” but instead from the older meanings of **h₂eng-/h₂enǵʰ-/*h₂emǵʰ-* “stiff firm pole” and “pointed”, then that’s very likely to be correct, especially since PIE **h₂eyǵ-*, “oak tree” is so similar to PIE **h₂eyǵ-* (“sharp, pointed, barb”), and PIE **h₂eǵ/*h₂eyǵ-* (“goat”) are so similar to PIE **h₂ek-/*h₂eyk-* = “sharp, pointed”, and **h₂ek-/*h₂eyk-* would have included the meanings “stiff, hard, strong” as well, explaining Iranian words such as Old Median *asan* (“stone”) better than assuming that the meaning “stone” developed only from stones being used as cutting and stabbing tools. The *Asn* in the Moesian-Daco(?)–Thracian Kjolmen inscription, which I interpret as meaning “to cut, strike, gouge,

7 The Slavic word (*v*)*qzľ* ‘knot’ is itself of not quite clear extraction, because the traditional etymology (from PIE **h₂enǵʰ-/*h₂emǵʰ-*) doesn’t provide an obvious explanation for the acute. So again a variant of **h₂enǵʰ-/*h₂emǵʰ-* may be the source of (*v*)*qzľ*.

8 Derksen says the initial **v-* of **vĕzàti* is “unclear”; Vasmer attributes it to contamination with **verzti*, “to tie, squeeze”; while Chernykh sees contamination with **viti*, “to twist, to bend” (which is from Proto-Balto-Slavic **wīʔtei*, from PIE **weh₁y-* “to twist, wind, weave, plait; to wrap, enclose, cover”. The initial *V* before the vowels in these cases is probably simply a common Balto-Slavic phenomenon, encountered for example in many of the Slavic words deriving from Proto-Slavic *qzľ* ‘knot’.

stab” may derive from PIE $*h_2ek-$, “sharp, pointed” as does Old Median *asan* (“stone”). I do not think that *Asn* in the inscription means stone, since I expect that *Katroso* in the inscription means “stone”.

It remains perhaps for linguists of the future (perhaps aided by new archaeological finds) to determine which theory is correct: do these Baltic oak tree words (excluding *aižuols*, which is from PIE $*h_2eyǵ-$ for sure) derive from “twisted, gnarled”, in turn from “knotty/knotted<knot<tight” from PIE $*h_2eng^h-/*h_2emǵ^h-$? Do they derive from PIE $*h_2eng-$, “to turn, curve, bend” (but the root $*h_2eng-$ may not have actually had the meanings “to turn, curve, bend”, though such meanings may have developed post-PIE) or from a folk-etymological association of PIE $*h_2eyǵ-$ with PIE $*h_2eng-$ “to turn, curve, bend”?

Do they derive from a late (Proto-Baltic) folk-etymological blending of $*h_2eyǵ-/*h_2eǵ-$ (“oak tree”) with *heng-* words that meant “knotty”, with the *heng-* words deriving from $*h_2eng^h-/*h_2emǵ^h-$? Do they derive, as I argue for my primary theory, from an early PIE form (or a little after PIE form) $*h_2eng^h-/*h_2emǵ^h-$ which meant “tight, firm pole, tree trunk”, “something long, stiff, narrow/narrowish and rising”, “something pointed”? Do they derive from PIE $*g^welh_2-$, “acorn”, as one or more linguists have argued in the past? Did PIE $*h_1óg^whis/*h_3ég^whis$ (“snake, dragon”) play a role, as one or more linguists have suggested (but I doubt that very much, despite the Baltic forms from $*h_3ég^whis$ being similar to Old Prussian *anzonis*, “oak tree”)? Does PIE $*h_1óg^whis/*h_3ég^whis$ have anything to do with “narrow” referring to the snake’s body, as I posit, the first one to do so⁹? Or to the sharp, pointed fangs of snakes, as I posit, also the first one to do so? Did PIE $*h_2eyǵ-$ (“oak tree”) and PIE $*h_2eyǵ-/*h_2eǵ-$ (“goat”) derive from the older meaning “to turn, curve, bend, twist”, referring to the branches and the trunk and roots of the oak tree, and to the twisting horns of goats? I doubt it. I considered that for some months but I found that $*h_2eyǵ-$ (“oak tree”) and PIE $*h_2eyǵ-/*h_2eǵ-$ (“goat”) more likely came from the older meanings that I argue for in this paper and in my other papers, and I have shown compelling indications that any “twisted, curved, bent” meanings would have come later, and the ancient PIE roots for “oak tree” and “goat” more likely come from the original meanings, which work better for oak trees, acorns and goats.

For my explanation of PIE $*h_2eyǵ-$, “goat” from a root that meant “stiff, pointed, projecting” and the other meanings detailed earlier, compare English “stag” (=an adult male deer; a colt or filly), Middle English *stagge*, *steg*, Old

9 I first posited both of these theories about the root-meaning of PIE $*h_1óg^whis/*h_3ég^whis$ (“narrow” referring to the snake’s body or “pointed, sharp” referring to the fangs) in an Academia.edu Sessions in September/early October 2022, a Sessions for Nicolás Monti’s paper “East Baltic $*ā$ vs $*ō$ and their Proto-Indo-European sources”. Some other ideas I also first posited in that Sessions, which had 38 participants. I also posited in that Sessions an additional theory that the earlier meaning of $*h_1óg^whis/*h_3ég^whis$ could have been “twisted, turning”, from “knot”, from “tight, narrow”.

English *stagga*, *stacga*, Old Norse *steggi*, *steggr* (“a male animal”), Icelandic *steggi*, *steggur* (=tomcat, male fox), Proto-Germanic **staggijô*, **staggijaz* (=male, male deer, porcupine)---but for PIE **h₂eyǵ-*, “goat” I think it also carried the meaning “lascivious, horny” (compare English “horny”, and the tomcat/male fox/male deer, male animal meanings of *stag/steg*) and likely also “climber, mounter”. For more evidence for my interpretation of PIE **h₂e(y)ǵ-*, “goat” and PIE **h₂e(y)ǵ-*, “oak tree”, see my work on the Moesian Kjolmen inscription, where I discuss evidence such as Ancient Greek *αἰγίς*, which meant “the pith/center/heartwood of a pine tree”, which I derive from *αἰγίς*=“point; pointed”, as seen with Ancient Greek *κέντρον* meaning “something with a sharp point, spike, spur, barb” and also meant “central point”, hence *κέντρον* is the source of English *center*, Romanian *centru*, French *centre*, and so on.

3.

The PIE root **kel-* most likely meant “to cover”, as stated in a number of authoritative works, and so did not have an older meaning of “skin, hide”, as some think. In this work I argue that the meaning “to cover” found in PIE **kel-* in turn came from “to project horizontally”: if so, then PIE **kel-* is cognate with a PIE root in Pokorny’s IEW, found on pages 552-553: PIE **kel-* “thin shaft, stalk”:

PIE **kel-* ‘dünnere Schaft, Pfeil, steifer Halm’

Material: Ai. *śalá-* m. ‘Stock, Stachel des Stachelschweins’ [“Stachel des Stachelschweins” means “needles of a porcupine”], *śalala-* n., *śalalī* ‘Stachel des Stachelschweins’, *śalyá-* m. n. ‘Pfeilspitze, Speerspitze, Dorn, Stachel’, *śalyaká-* m. ‘Stachelschwein [=porcupine]’; dial. Nebenform ablaut. *śila-* m. ‘Ähre’ = lit. *šilas* ‘Heide’; dazu *śará-* ‘Rohr, Pfeil’, *śáru-* ‘Pfeil, Speer’;

unsicher arm. ‘*śalart*’ ‘belaubter Zweig, langes Haar’;

gr. κῆλον ‘Pfeil, Geschöß’;

mir. *cail* ‘Speer’, *celtair* f. ‘Speer(spitze)’;

anord. *hali* m. ‘Spitze eines Schaftes, Schwanz’;

apr. *kelian* ‘Speer’ mit westidg. *k* für *k̂*; lit. *šilas* ‘Heide’ (nach den starren Stengeln).

This PIE “thin shaft, stalk” I expect comes from “thin shaft; stalk; something narrow and stiff that projects vertically; pointed; etc.” as we saw with many PIE roots beginning with *ste-*: from the meaning “to project out/to project

horizontally” developed to “to stretch, to spread” (“to spread” leaving aside the “narrow” connotation) which led to “to cover”.

I also posit that PIE **ker-*, “to grow” comes from the earlier meaning “to rise, sprout” (and compare also PIE **kerh₂-*, “horn; head; top”), in turn from the same set of meanings encountered with PIE **kel*, “thin shaft, stalk”. And I posit that PIE **ker-*, “to plait, weave; rope, cord” comes from the earlier meaning “to make tight”, in turn from “stiff”, in turn from “something stiff, erect, pointed, projecting”.

I posit that PIE **kerd*, “heart” (later becoming **kér* in late Proto-Indo-European with compensatory lengthening) comes from either from 1) “central point”, in turn from “pointed, stiff” (compare how Ancient Greek *κέντρον*=“something with a sharp point: spike, spur, barb” led to “point in the center”, which led to the meaning “center”: Ancient Greek *κέντρον* is the source of English “center”; *κέντρον* is from PIE **kent-* “to prick; pointed”); or 2) from “hard pit of a fruit”, in turn from “hard, stiff” from a root that meant “hard, stiff, strong, firm, erect, narrow¹⁰, projecting, pointed, sharp” and so on as detailed earlier with the **ste-* roots. This is indicated also by the Nw. Germanic dialectal word *hort*=“tough piece of bark, gnarl”, with “gnarl” akin to “knot”, from “tight, firm”, and seen by “*tough* piece of bark”: Kroonen 2013 says that that *hort* word is cognate with the Germanic heart words. The Germanic words of the “*harta*” type meaning “pitch, resin” derive, as Kroonen implies, from the older implied meaning “from the pith, core”, so we are not dealing with a root that meant “to trickle; ooze, flow; wet; slimy”, which could have applied to numerous inner organs---but that’s not what the evidence shows in this case. For such a case, see the etymology of English *liver*, from a root that meant “sticky, slimy; wet”. PIE **kers-* “to run” seems to derive from the same semantic progression encountered with PIE **steyg^h-* “to go; climb”: PIE **kers-* “to run” probably developed from the earlier meaning “to project forward; shoot forward like an arrow”: compare how Ancient Greek *ὀξύς* means “sharp, pointed (especially of swords, axes, etc.)” and also “quick, swift, fast, hasty” and “sharp, keen, clever” (and also dazzling, bright; of sounds: shrill, piercing, high, sharp; of tastes, pungent, sharp, acid).

Closely akin to Pokorny’s PIE **kel-* “thin shaft, stalk” is PIE **kolh₂mos*/**kólh₂-m₆* ~ **klh₂-ém-*, source of Ancient Greek *κᾶλᾶμος*¹¹ (“a reed; cane; staff, rod; pen; shaft of an arrow; flute; collectively, of plants which are neither bush nor tree); cognates include Latin *culmus*; Proto-Slavic **solma*

10 With meanings such as “stone” and “hard pit of a fruit” and “wood”, the meaning “narrow” was not included, only “stiff; strong, hard, firm” and such meanings as those.

11 I’ve have seen two derivations for *κᾶλᾶμος*: one derives the word from **kolh₂mos* via a [zero-grade](#) variant **klh₂mos*, while Beekes posited that *κᾶλᾶμος* was independently [thematicized](#) from an original ablauting paradigm **kólh₂-m₆* ~ **klh₂-ém-*.

(="straw"), Proto-Balto-Slavic **sál²mā²* ("straw"; see Lithuanian *salms*, Old Prussian *salme*, etc.), Proto-Germanic **halmaz* ("halm, stem, stalk; straw, hay"). PIE **kólh₂mos*/**kólh₂-m₆* ~ **k¹lh₂-ém-* in turn is considered to derive from PIE **kélh₂-*, "to stick, prick, stab".

Other roots that are part of the **kél*/**kel-* group meaning "stiff, hard, pointed, sharp; to project" are PIE **(s)kelH-*/**(s)kel-*/**(s)kelh₂*~**(s)kelh₃*, "to cut; to split, to separate"; PIE **kelh₂*, "to beat, to break"; PIE **kelH-*, to prick, jab (into), thrust (into)"; PIE **kelH-*, "to rise; to be tall; hill"; the Arabic root q-l-m="to cut, to clip, to pare, to prune, to trim, to lop, to truncate, to snip, to cut back, to cut down; to make stripes, to stripe; to fleece, to fleece wool".

If PIE **kél-*, "to cover" does not derive from the earlier meaning "to project horizontally" as I argue in this paper, then it may derive from "to cut", from a root that meant "stiff, sharp, pointed", leading to "to cut", in turn leading to "that which is cut", referring to "hide, skin", and from there meaning "to cover (as if covering with hide, skin)"¹². PIE **kél-*, "to cover" may also derive from "to cover with straw", from "straw", but I prefer a derivation from "to project horizontally", because **kél-*, "to cover" is an aniṭ root, among other reasons. Etruscan *Cel* (an Earth goddess) is probably from "projecting horizontally; flat>to cover" and cognate to PIE **kél-*, "to cover".

PIE **kes-* "to cut", is from "sharp, pointed, hard, stiff".

PIE **keh₁s-* "to teach, indicate" may come from the older meaning "to point out"/"to point"/"the index finger"/"something long, narrow, pointed, stiff" etc. There may also have been the semantic "to implant" involved, "to implant" from "to stick in", from "stick; stiff; firm; pointed".

PIE **key-*, "to settle; to be lying down" probably derives from "to dig in, stick in, stiff, firm, planted in", and "lying down" also has the idea of "stretched out", from "to project horizontally/projecting/stiff". There also was a PIE **key-*, "to go; to move" which I derive from "to project forward", from "something projecting; long and stiff, etc."

I no longer suppose that the *Kinna-* in *Kinnabari(s)* (=cinnabar) is so close to Ancient Greek *κινέω* (which is from PIE **key-*, "to go, move", and *κινέω* did not actually mean "to flow", nor did I claim that that meaning was attested) : instead they are probably distant cognates or independent parallels from a kindred verbal-semantic reflex: because I now expect that the *Kinna-* in *Kinnabari(s)* meant "stone" not "blood", and derives not from "to flow; move" but instead from "hard; stiff; erect; pointed; sharp", and *Kinna-* meaning "stone" was most likely Non-IE but exhibiting what I referred to as "a kindred verbal-semantic reflex"

12 This derivation of PIE **kél-*, "to cover" from "to cut>that which is cut>hide, skin" I first published in 2021 or 2020 in my work on the etymology of the Getan-Thracian theonym *Zalmoxis*.

where k/\acute{k} =”stiff, strong, pointed, sharp, projecting”, an association not exclusive to IE languages: there are so many examples I could cite in Non-IE, but for now I will cite only a few like Sumerian *Kin*=”mountain” and Sumerian *Kur*=”mountain”.

I posit that the *Kina-* in Hattic *Kinawar* (=”copper”) most likely meant “metal/stone” from *Kina*=“hard/strong/stiff”, while “-*War*” meant either “red” or more likely “soft” or “pliable, bending” (copper is a rather soft, malleable metal), and the *Kinna/Tinga/Tianga/Tunga* in Ancient Greek *κιννάβαρι* (*kinnábari*), *κιννάβαρις* (*kinnábaris*), *τιγγάβαρι* (*tingábari*), *τιγγάβαρυ* (*tingábaru*), *τιαγγάβαρι* (*tiangábari*), *τυγγάβαρι* (*tungábari*)---all Ancient Greek words for “cinnabar”, I posit meant “stone”, from the earlier meaning “hard, stiff, strong”, and I think very likely cognate with Phrygian *Teama*, a word which per Lubotsky (et al.?) very likely meant “stone”: Phrygian *Teama* and *Tianga* in the Ancient Greek variant are quite similar. The Phrygian word is also found with the variant *Ateama* (I think the *A-* is a euphonic *A*, as encountered sometimes in Ancient Greek and other languages), and there are other variants in Phrygian as well.

The *Bari/Baris/Baru* found in those Ancient Greek words likely meant either “red” or more likely “soft” or “crumbling; friable, brittle”: a second Ancient Greek word for “cinnabar” is *ψάδδα* (*psadda*) which most likely had the older meaning “crumbling, friable, brittle” referring to the crumbly nature of cinnabar: see Ancient Greek *ψᾶθῦρός* /*ψαδυρόν*=”friable, crumbly, brittle”.

The Old Persian word *sinkabruš* meant “carnelian”, but if the earlier meaning was “cinnabar” then the *bruš* portion of the word is very likely from PIE **b^hrews-*”to break”¹³, and cognate with Albanian *breshër/bresh* (“hail”), Dutch *broos* (“brittle”), Latin *frustum* (“shard”), et al. The *Sinka-* portion of *sinkabruš* and the Ancient Greek *Tianga, Tinga, Tunga* are very close to Persian and Middle Persian *sang* (“stone, rock”), Parthian *asang* “stone”, Old Persian *aθa^{ga}^h* “stone, rock”, Old Median *asan* (“stone”), Khotanese *samgga-* (“stone”)---these *sang/asang/asan/aθa^{ga}^h/samgga-* words are believed to derive (and I believe they do derive) from PIE **h₂eḱ-* “sharp”, which I argue also meant “stiff, hard”, though such meanings were lost in many IE languages: those were early PIE/Proto-PIE

13 *Bari/Baris/Baru* and Hattic *-war* (in *Kinawar*) would not be from PIE **b^hrews-*”to break”, rather seems like Iranian switched the presumably Non-IE *Bari/Baris/Baru/-War* words for an IE *Brush* word deriving from **b^hrews-*”to break”. Likewise, *Kin(n)a*=stone was probably non-IE and Iranian speakers may have switched *Kin(n)a* for IE/IE-like *Sink-*: or, Iranian took the word *Sinkabruš* from a language that switched the terms---but at the same time, I think that *Kinna* and *Sinka* are cognates, but *Kinna* cannot be from PIE **h₂eḱ-* “sharp”: so then *Sinka* most likely is not from PIE **h₂eḱ-* “sharp”, but instead from a root (likely Non-IE, but see **seng^h-* “ant, bee”) of a different form which had the same semantic range as **h₂eḱ-*.

meanings passed on only in a few IE languages: I believe that those Indic “stone” words that I cited above derive from “stiff, hard” not from “cutting, sharp”.

Witczak derives¹⁴ Old Prussian *sangis* (“ant”), Albanian *thnegël*¹⁵ (“ant”), Irish *seangán* (“ant”), Central Kurdish *heng* (“bee”) et al. from a proto-form **seng^h-* which he says meant “ant” and/or “bee”. I agree that all those words are cognates, but I’m not sure if they trace back to a **seng^h-*, since there were likely variants beginning with Ts-, etc. And very importantly, I believe that the older meaning was “stinger (for the ant, the sting of the ant bite, or more generally for the bug, the sting of a bug bite)/sting”, from the older meanings “pointed, sharp, stiff, strong, projecting, tight, narrow”---the latter two which meanings can be seen in Irish *seang*, “thin, slender”, from Middle Irish *seng* (“id.”). The meaning was not “small”, because that would most likely have been seen in Irish. And the bee emphasis in Central Kurdish *heng* and some other examples speaks for “sting/stinger”.

Basque *txingurri/xinaurri/zinaurri/inaurri* all meaning “ant” are derived by Trask’s etymological dictionary of Basque¹⁶ from a proto-form **ziNaguRi*: I posit that the Zina- portion meant “biter/stinger”, from Zin= “stiff, sharp, pointed, tight, strong, projecting”. English “ant” is from Proto-West-Germanic **āmaitijā*, which is thought by a number of authorities to have meant “biting-thing, cutter”: there are other examples of ant/small bug words and spider words deriving from “biter, cutter”.

Sanskrit हिङ्गुल/ *hingula*, which means 1)vermillion; 2)cinnabar; 3)a medicinal drug, levigated cinnabar, may derive from a lost word for the Kermes worm from which a vermillion/crimson/carmine/red pigment was and is extracted: if Hing- was the beginning portion of a word for the Kermes worm, Hing- had to refer to how the Kermes worm bores/cuts/bites through the wood of trees, and Hing- would have meant “hard, sharp, cutting, stiff”, and this indicates that PIE **h₂éng^{whis}* “snake” came from either from **h₂éng=* “tight, narrow” referring to the snake’s body and/or from **h₂éng=* “sharp, pointed” referring to the snake’s fangs. And most likely PIE **h₁óg^{whis}* had the same root-meaning(s) as **h₂éng^{whis}*. The PIE root of Kermes is **k^wṛ^mis*, said to have meant “worm”: many worms bore through things, so I think that **k^wṛ^mis* meant “borer”, from **k^wṛ-* probably a combination of Kw= “sharp, stiff, pointed, hard” (see my theoretical **Kwet*, source of Ancient Greek Petra= “stone” and see other evidence for **kwet* detailed in some of my other works) and PIE **wer-*, “to turn, bend”, the likely source of PIE **w^rm^{is}*, “worm”.

14 Krzysztof Tomasz Witczak, “The Albanian name for badger”, *Zeitschrift für Balkanologie* 47, no. 2 (2011): 244; and also in at least one other work of his.

15 With a number of variant forms in Albanian.

16 *Etymological Dictionary of Basque* by R. L. Trask.

Ancient Greek κίνναμον, κίνναμον, κινάμων, Hebrew *kinamón* and Phoenician *qinnamon* all meant “cinnamon”: in another work of mine I detailed the problems and uncertainties that arise when assuming that the Kin(n)- in these words derives from a Chinese element *Dzin*¹⁷---beyond the phonological problems, it is most likely that (maybe even already a fact that) the Ancient Egyptians and others in the West imported cinnamon from Sri Lanka before they imported cinnamon from China.

Therefore beginning in 2020, I hypothesized that Kinna meant “red/red-brown” and also “purple”, and I cited Hurrian *Kinahhu/Kinahnu* thought by some (after Ephraim Avigdor Speiser first posited the theory in 1938) to have been a synonym for red or purple dye. The fact that the Latin word *minium* was applied to cinnabar, red lead and to red cinnamon added more likelihood to my early theory.

But my new theory, which I’m detailing in this paper and which I will expand/detail/refine in future editions of this work, is that the Kin(n)/Qin(n) in Kinnamon/Qinnamon likely meant “bark of a tree”, from “hard, tough, stiff”, which would mean that *Kin(n)abari(s)* and *Kin(n)am(om)on* come from closely related languages if not from the same language. If the Hurrian terms *Kinahhu/Kinahnu*, actually referred to red/purple dye, then it may be from a lost word for the spiny Murex (and I posit that Latin Murex is from Mur=“pointed, stiff, hard”, see the meanings of Murex in Latin and see Semitic Marr=“bitter”, which is probably from “stinging, pungent” from “pointed, stiff”, since Marr also meant “sharp” in Arabic and since Marra means “shovel, spade” in Aramaic and “shovel, spade, mattock, hoe, mallet” in Classical Syriac, from Akkadian Mar=shovel, spade; see also Ancient Greek μάρρον=“iron spade” and Latin *marra*=“hoe, hook”), from which a purple dye was extracted by the Phoenicians/Tyrians (Tyrian purple), a lost word for the spiny Murex that began with Kin-.

In Ancient Greek, we also find a word κίννα (*kinna*)=*Hordeum murinum*, known in English as Wall Barley (growing besides road walls, ruins and unkempt homes, etc.), Way Barley (growing on roadsides), False Barley, Hare Barley (grains eaten by hares), Mouse Barley (grains eaten by mice; Latin *murinum* in the modern Linnean name of the plant is a reference to “mouse” as well---not to walls; but no such mouse name for the plant is attested in actual Latin, nor a word referring to walls), Purr Barley (comparing the bristly/furry heads to cat’s fur), Pussies (comparing the bristly/furry heads to cat’s fur and to female pubic hair) et

17 This theory mostly based on an Iranian word for cinnamon, *dârčîn*, literally “Chinese tree” (*dâr*=tree). However, *Dzin* seems to have yielded *Thin* and *Sin* in Ancient Greek, not *Kin*/*Qin*, and there’s no evidence that *Dzin* would have yielded *Kin*/*Qin* in Phoenician or Hebrew. Maybe in some other language.

al.: in December 2020, I posited that κίννα referred to the deep crimson/cinnamon color that very often appears on mature barley spikes (a deep crimson/cinnamon color which, as far as I have ascertained so far, does not appear on true barley): I'm now quite sure that κίννα actually referred to the long spikes of the *H. murinum*, which are referenced in *margall* (which I link with Breton *marg*=”clay”, from the older meaning “rocks, pebbles, grit”, as seen in Welsh *marian*=”rocks, pebbles, grit” from Brythonic **marg-*; and I link also PIE **morg-*, “edge, boundary, border”, which I think is either from “boundary stone<stone” or from “edge<straight line<stiff, rigid, hard, pointed, sharp”¹⁸) a Catalan word for *H. murinum* as well as for Ryegrass (=any of several tufted grasses of the genus *Lolium*), and the spikes/bristles are referenced as well in English Purr Barley and Pussies, and surely in other words for this plant in other languages.

One of the deciding votes in favor of κίννα=”spike, stone, stiff, hard, pointed, erect” rather than κίννα =crimson is Ancient Greek κίνναβος, κάναβος, κάνναβος=”wooden framework round which artists molded; lean person, skeleton”: the root-meaning was “narrow, stiff; projecting; stick; pole; post; cane, tree-trunk”, and I expect that Ancient Greek *κάννᾶ/κάννη* (=giant reed) and Akkadian *qanûm* (reed, cane, arrow, pipe) are from a kindred/cognate Kan=”stiff, projecting, narrow, pointed” and so on.

I derive Ancient Greek *κάννᾶβις* and *κάνναβος* from *κάννᾶ*=”rising, projecting vertically, high-sprouting”, from “pole, tree-trunk, narrow, projecting, stiff, strong, pointed, sharp”: cannabis often grows to 20 feet high and heights of 34 feet have been recorded, though I'm not sure how often such a 34 foot height has been recorded or whether they've been bred to grow as high as 34 feet more recently---in any case, cannabis plants, even the 7 foot and 5 foot ones, are very high for a non-tree herb-like plant, and therefore very remarkable (compare how words for the fennel plant often refer to their height). Alternatively, referring to hemp-cords, with “cord” deriving from “that which tightens”, from “tight, stiff, narrow, pointed” etc. Sumerian *kunibu* (cannabis) must have the same earlier meaning (s), but the word is not necessarily of Sumerian origin: Sumerian has a number of roots in common with PIE.

I derive the PIE root **kormō-*”ermine, weasel, stoat, cat,” (a Germano-Baltic isogloss) from the earlier “furry/bristly/hairy” with “bristly/hairy” deriving from “to project, stiff, hard” etc.; cats/wildcats have been in Europe since before 7,000 BC, so the word could have referred to “cat” (not referring to the big cats: panthers, lions, etc.) as long ago as the ermines, stoats, weasels, etc.---since the

18 I don't agree with one etymology that derives Catalan *margall* (wall-barley) from *amarus*, Latin for “bitter”, supposedly because wall-barley grains taste bitter---do they though? How bitter? If Ancient Greek *kinna* is from a Pre-Greek word for “pointed/stiff”,etc. that would have included “bitter” as well as bristly/spiky.

word actually meant “furry, bristly”. The cat meaning is attested in Lithuanian *šarmuō*, *šermuō* = “wildcat, stoat, weasel”.

I derive Latin *cattus* (= “cat”)/Proto-Germanic **kattuz*¹⁹ from *Katt* = “furry/bristly”, akin to PIE **kayt/kāyt-* = “heather; forest; grassland/pasturage”: those meanings I posit came from “that which rises, sprouts” in turn probably from “stiff, projecting” not from “to blow out, swell”: “blow out, swell” doesn’t jibe with the later (but still roughly PIE) meaning “wasteland”. Nor does a root-meaning “rocky (land)” work, that doesn’t match “forest” and “grassland/pasturage” that well: the later meaning “wasteland” developed from “heath”, in turn from “sprouting”.

An alternative derivation for **kormō-* and *cattus/kattuz* would be to derive them from the earlier meaning “cut, split” leading to “vagina” leading to “stoat, weasel, cat” (compare Hungarian *hölgy* < *helgy* meaning “lady; weasel”, but I prefer to derive that pair from “bristly, furry” leading on the one hand to vagina and on the other to weasel): while “cut/split” in this case would be from “sharp, pointed, stiff > that which cuts > to cut”. For *cattus/kattuz* one might also posit “little sprout”, because little cats are so much like miniature big cats: but I doubt that’s the one. If it were the one, then “little sprout” could be from “to sprout/project up/stiff/pointed” or from “to swell out, to blow” (a totally different kind of root-word, unrelated to “stiff, hard, sharp, pointed”) or from “to split open” leading to “bloom (from “to open”)” and to “sprout” (seeds splitting open and pushing out a sprout): this semantic from “to cut/split” to “to sprout” is encountered in Albanian *çel* = “to open, sprout, come out, hatch”, already known to derive from PIE **(s)kelH-* “(to) split(apart)”.

Latin *cattus*/Germanic **kattuz* are probably also akin to a little-known Ancient Greek (most likely from Thracian for reasons that will be detailed; and attested after Ancient Greek times) *koṭys* meaning “anchor”, most likely from the earlier meaning “cat” as I will detail, because many/most anchors have those two prongs sticking up like a cat’s ears and shaped a lot like a cat’s ears: for many

19 Not proven to be from Latin *cattus*. Compare also Proto-Uralic **kādʷä*. The root-meaning of Proto-Uralic **kādʷä* was probably “bristly/hairy”, then meaning “vagina, vulva”, then meaning “female”: explaining all the words in Finno-Ugric and Uralic, which include Mator *kejbe*, “mare”; words meaning “stoat, ermine”, and Hungarian *hölgy* < *helgy* = “lady; weasel”. I do not consider Proto-Uralic **kādʷä* to be the source of the IE forms, there is too much in IE of such a nature; so I consider these to be in common between PIE/IE and Proto-Uralic, and likely additional language families. The Chilean Indigenous term *kodkod* referring to an indigenous little wildcat (*Leopardus guigna*; they are about half the size of a domestic wildcat) of southern [Andean](#) and coastal ranges, particularly the [Valdivian](#) and [Araucaria](#) forests of Chile, is possibly a cognate despite the extraordinary time and distance involved in bringing the root-word from East Asia to Chile: but it’s likely that the root-meaning of *kodkod* was “small” since it would have reminded them of a miniature leopard, and “small” would most likely not be cognate (unless “small” came from “little piece cut off” < to cut < sharp, pointed, stiff”); the *kodkod* has rather short hair. “Kod” could have meant “a little sprout” (comparing the small cat to a sproutling), with “sprout” deriving from “to project; stem; stiff; pointed”.

anchors, very much looking like a cat's ears/cat's head (no one has deduced this in modern times besides me, but that's the origin of the association), while other anchors not so much. This resemblance of many anchors to a cat's head/ears is encountered in English ("Cathead" in English sailor-talk refers to the beam from which the anchor is lowered and the beam to which the anchor is fastened when brought back up, and a Cat's Head/Lion's head was often sculpted on the anchor-holding the beam for that reason, as I deduced²⁰), Slavic (see **koty*="anchor", certainly cognate to **kòtъ*="cat", as is often argued, though no one before me in modern times has figured out the connection), Romanian (see *cătușă*="cat; anchor"²¹, both from Latin *cattus*, but the meaning „anchor" is not attested in Latin), and in German (see Middle Low German *katt*="small anchor" and *katt* also means "cat" in some Germanic languages, rather than *Katze/Kater/Kätzin* in standard German) and perhaps/most likely in another languages as well.

Before me, there is at least one linguist, Шапошников, А. К. (2018), who realized that Ancient Greek *κότυς / kotys* (anchor) is from Thracian and cognate to Thracian *Κότυς / Kotys* (=a Thracian male/unisex anthroponym and the name of a Thracian Artemis, but apparently with more emphasis on battle than Artemis had in traditional Ancient Greece), with the variant form *Kottyto*, and also cognate to Slavic **koty*="anchor" and to Slavic **kòtъ*="cat"---but he did not explain the root-meanings, he did not explain how the "anchor" meaning is related to the "cat" meaning, nor did he explain how *Kotys* the Thracian Artemis fits in: now I will try to explain how *Kotys* the Thracian Artemis fits in: the root-word which led to "bristly, furry" which led to "cat" (*kotys*, unattested in the meaning "cat" but deduced/theorized from the attested meaning "anchor") had the older meanings that I described earlier, same as PIE **kayt/*kayt*, so words meaning "sprouting, forest, grasslands" would have come from that root as well, as well as words meaning "arrow-shaft/arrow"/"spear-shaft/spear"/"point of a spear/point of an arrow" (one known example: see Old Church Slavonic *ratiste*="shaft of an arrow", cognate to Latin *Retae*, "trees along a river-bank" and cognate to Latin *Ratis*="raft, boat" from the older meanings "wood posts, wood beams; tree trunks;

20 A second "cat head" was associated with a ship's anchor-cable and [windlass](#). This was a square pin thrust into one of the handspike holes of a ship's windlass. When at anchor, the anchor rope (called a cable or [catfall](#)) was secured to this with a smaller rope tie called a [seizing](#). The English term for this pin was 'Norman'. In German, however, it was called a *Kattenkopf* (cat-head), and in this case it may be a reference to the traditional way the top was notched and chamfered off so that in cross section, it resembled the ears of a cat.

21 And *cătușă* also means in Romanian: "handcuff/manacle", "mousetrap" and "trap, snare". The meaning "cat" led to "mousetrap": from comparing a mousetrap to a cat for obvious reasons; the meaning "mousetrap" led to "trap, snare" and the meanings "trap, snare" led to "handcuff/manacle". I am probably first to correctly describe these semantic progressions.

sticks”, and Dacian Rathi- in Dacian Rathibida=*Chenopodium vulvaria*; on Nov 12, 2022, before 10:00 am, I published in an Academia sessions that the “Bida” in Dacian Rathibida is cognate to Sanskrit Bhida (“to split apart”) and Latin findo (“to split apart”) and I stated that Bida meant “vulva” in Dacian, from PIE **b^heyd-*, “to split”, because in many languages the word for the plant means “vulva plant” because of the way the plant smells like a stinky (not a clean) vulva: compare German Schamkraut (Scham is a German word “vulva”, and kraut=herb, plant), English Notchweed: here “notch”, which usually means a “split, cut” means “vulva”). One may think that the anchor word kotys comes from “kot”=“stiff, strong, thick”, or from “projecting up” (the prongs pointing up) but more likely the “anchor” meaning developed from “cat” because anchors often look like cats’ heads, the prongs often looking like pointed cat ears.

As seen in examples such as Ancient Greek Oxus, a word meaning “sharp, pointed” can also mean “bright”, and that chimes with the moon-goddess aspect of Kotys/Artemis. I do not accept a derivation of Kotys from PIE **kéh₃tus*, “fight”, from PIE **kéh₃*, “to fight”, because that forces the scenario that kotys (anchor) is not cognate to Kotys, which I find very unlikely, and “fight” is very distant from anchor; furthermore the root-meaning of **kéh₃* was probably “to burn; be angry; passionate”: the meaning “burn” can chime with the moon, but more with the sun, while “anger” doesn’t fit Artemis most of the time. There may have been a blending of **kéh₃*, “to fight” with **Kot*, “to sprout; pointed; bright; stiff; sharp, bristly” in Thracian. I argue that PIE **keh₂-* “to desire, wish” also comes from “burning”, as does the Cassis (=shining, bright) in Scythian Krou-Cassis (Krou=“frost” already known to be cognate to Ancient Greek kruos, “frost” et al., from Kr=“hard, stiff, to thicken, congeal; strong”, cognate to Ancient Greek κρόκη =“pebble”).

Proto-Slavic **stǫblъ*=“wildcat” is known to ultimately be from PIE **stǫbъ*=“stem, stalk, cane, bristle” from a set of meanings including “stiff” and “strong”: I have seen the explanation that the “wildcat” meaning developed from “fierce<stiff, hard”, which is probably correct, because that progression may be confirmed in Slavic and it is seen in some other languages; but the derivation may instead be from bristly/furry: but then I would expect **stǫblъ* to also mean “stoat, ermine” etc.. Either way, Proto-Slavic **stǫblъ*=“wildcat” lends more credence/likelihood to my theory that Cattus and Kotys derive from a root meaning “bristly, stiff, hard, projecting” and the other meanings I described: but I don’t think that cattus is from “fierce”, because then it would have applied more to wolves, panthers, bears, etc. “Fierce” may be intended to some degree for Kotys, especially since it was also a male given name: this would work better than

thinking Kotys meant “fighter”. Or Kotys could just have meant “strong, firm”, or “sprouting” (compare Latin Florinus).

I posit that Ancient Greek *θρίξ* (hair; used also for an animal’s bristly hair, for a lark’s crest), *θριγκός/θριγγός/θριγχός* (=topmost course of stones in a wall, cornice, coping; used of a row of slabs behind a frieze; coping-stone, last finish; wall, fence; row, frieze) both derive from the earlier meanings “stiff, erect, narrow, projecting (vertically or horizontally), sprouting, rising, a line, a row, a bristle, a spike, tight, hard”. It’s unclear whether the root had initial **d^h*-, but likely it did. In my work on the etymologies of Ancient Greek *thrion* (fig leaf), *Thriambos*, *thridax*=lettuce (and the many variants of *thridax*), *Thriai*, I derived all those from *Thri*=“to flow”, for reasons detailed in that work. And I do not think that *thridax* instead derives from “to sprout up”, because the milky sap of lettuce is much more striking and worthier of being the main reference for a lettuce plant (see my work on *Thridax* and see Latin *Lactuca*=lettuce, from *Lactis*=milk). The meaning “to flow/to run” could have developed from “to project out/forward”, which would obviously mean that the meanings “stiff, narrow, tight, pointed, hard, sharp” are older and the meaning “to flow” came later in this case.

The *Trik-* in Lycian *Trikasbos* (*asbos*=“horse”), as I explained in my translation of the Moesian *Kjolmen* inscription, meant “Up, top, rising”, and is cognate to Ancient Greek *θρίξ* and to *θριγκός/θριγγός/θριγχός*. *Trikasbos*=*Epihippos* (=“Up on the horse”, .e.g. on horseback, e.g. Horse-Rider/Horseman), as I explained in my paper on the Moesian *Kjolmen* inscription. Ancient Greek *Θαργήλια* (*Thargelia*), an agricultural festival in late May, takes its name from *Tharg*=“sprout”, as indicated by *thargelos*=“sprouted grain bread”, e.g. bread made from whole grains which have begun to sprout: the festival was likely not simply named after the grain bread, but instead would have also referred to the sprouting that bears some fruit (from certain plants, and I don’t refer only literally to fruits) by late May.

I posit that the *Tark-* in Hieroglyphic Luwian *Tarkasna* (donkey, ass) is from “stiff, hard, pointed, erect, sharp” leading “strong; firm; that which supports”, a stem that I believe also explains best the *Tork* in Armenian *Tork Angegh*, an Armenian mythological super-strong masculine male deity, similar to Hercules yet ugly like Hephaestus and like Hephaestus also a deity of manufacturing and the arts. *Angegh* means “ugly” from “twisted, crooked”. Latin *asinus* (“ass”) is likely from an unknown language where *As*=“hard, firm, strong, supporting”, from a wider set including *As*=“sharp, pointed, projecting” the likely source of Ancient Greek *Asia* (“rising”, “east”). Ancient Greek *Asis* “silt” is probably from “thick”, rather than from “dark”. And Latin *asinus* is probably also not from “dark”. Ancient Greek *Onos* (donkey, ass; hake fish; woodlouse; spindle, distaff) I’m sure

is from Pre-Greek On="hard, firm, strong; pointed, sharp", as indicated by Onos=hake fish. Onos=woodlouse may refer to the stiff shell of the woodlouse/pill-bug.

The Ancient Greek donkey and donkey-related terms beginning with Kanth- (κάνθων="pack-ass", etc.) and Anth- (άνθήλιον="pack-saddle") most likely derive from Kanth/Anth="stiff, firm, strong, hard, pointed, sharp" referring to how these animals carry heavy loads ("firm>supporting>bearing>carrying" also led to those Kanth- words meanings "panniers (κανθήλια), creels (κανθία)". The Rhodian Ancient Greek word ἄθρας /Athras (chariot) probably has the same explanation, from Athr="firm, strong, supporting>bearing>carrying", from a wider set including the meanings "pointed, sharp". The first part of the word κάρναθρον ("wicker carriage") is cognate to Kanabos ("a wooden framework; a slender, thin person"; see the discussion of Kanabos earlier), while -athron may be cognate to Athras ("carrier"), if not just a suffix, a suffix perhaps encountered in marathron, variant of marathon (fennel).

I've been sure for some time now (though I did not explain my reasons before) that Thracian Spartacus/Sparatakos/Sparadokus/Sparadokos does not derive from a conjectured Thracian *sparas ("spear, lance") combined with a badly conjectured Thracian *takos="famous": now I will explain: firstly, because I'm quite sure (from instinct and experience) that the fancy semantic progression which occurred with the Ancient Greek word δόξα---a shift over time from "expectation; opinion; judgment; belief" to "repute (from "opinion")" to "praise, glory, honor, magnificence" is unlikely to have occurred in a corresponding Thracian term (and the semantic progressions involved in the term even developing the earlier meanings "expectation; opinion" are not guaranteed in Thracian, since the PIE root **deǵ-* meant "to take; to perceive"), nor do I care to invoke a semantic borrowing from Ancient Greek, because the indications I get are that the -takus/-takos/-dakus/-dokos element in some Thracian names (including the name under discussion) is not cognate with Ancient Greek δόξα (nor to Ancient Greek *dokos*="holding"²²), and is in fact not even to be analyzed as beginning at the D sound: we are in fact dealing with an -akus/-akos/-okos suffix²³, and the D in all Thracian cases is the last letter of the word/stem that is being suffixed.

Now I will discuss the indications that I get that we are dealing with an -akus/-akos/-okos suffix similar and cognate to the Ancient Greek and Greek akos/-akis/-ake suffixes, and sometimes also -okos. There is a Thracian name and

22 Encountered in a number of Ancient Greek terms, check an Ancient Greek dictionary.

23 As Sorin Paliga realized and stated in one of his works published in the early 2000s.

oronym²⁴ Ἀμάδοκος, Amadokos, also Amatokos, perhaps more accurately Μήτοκος/Μήδοκος, Mētokos/Mēdokos, of which the Latin form would be Medocus: the application of this name to a *mountain* range rules of the interpretation of “tokos/dokos” as meaning “famous”, unless the mountain was named after a real or mythological person, which is quite unlikely. And the mountain application makes the “holding” interpretation unlikely, especially since Mēt/Mēd is not likely to have meant “sky” (nor does anyone claim that Mēt/Mēd meant “sky”), as if the mountain range were holding up the sky, supposing it was even such a high mountain range. So then, I expect the word is Amad (with prothetic and euphonic A most likely)/Mēt/Mēd, which I link to Ancient Epic Greek μήδεᾶ/μέζεα (=“male genitals”), with a root-meaning “stiff, hard, strong, erect, projecting, pointed, sharp”: explaining the mountain-range oronym, and the name could have meant “strong, firm” or “tall” among other possibilities, and polysemy is likely as well. I connect also Romanian *mazăre* (peas), Aromanian *madzãri/madzãre* (id.), Albanian *modhë* (brome grass, ryegrass, (dialectical) vetchling, vetch), and Albanian *modhull/modhullë/modull/modullë/motull/motullë/modhnë/modhël/modhëz* (=vetchling, yellow vetchling, vetch), from the projecting pea pods, not from “small bean” as shown by the meanings “brome; ryegrass”, which are more likely not a reference to the grains, judging from the usual cases for words for brome and ryegrass and other grasses like that: compare *Bromus erectus*, one of the common, widespread Brome species of Europe, known in English as “Erect brome” and “Upright brome” among other names. I compare also PIE **médʰyos* (= “middle”), which I derive from **médʰ*= “central point” from “point, pointed, stiff, firm, projecting, pole, tree-trunk”, better explaining Lithuanian *mēdis*=“tree, wood (material)”, Latvian *mežs*=“forest”, Old Prussian *median* (“forest”). And Μέδουσαῶ (Medousa>Medusa) is quite likely not from μέδω, “to protect, rule over” (despite dragons that protect their hordes, and other factors) but instead from “strong” or from “pointed fangs” (see Medusa’s fangs and tusks in older representations).

Additional evidence for my interpretation is seen in the Ancient Greek word πᾶρδακός/παρδοκός/πορδακός “wet, moist, damp”, a word of obscure etymology, and which is not claimed to be a compound in any work that I’ve seen. I mention this word rather than the many other Ancient Greek words with the -ακός suffix because it also has an -οκός variant.

So, Thracian Spart-/Sparat-/Sparad- is one stem and is cognate to Albanian *shpardh/shparth/shparr/shperdhë* (Gheg)/*shpardha* (Gheg)/*shpardhe* (Tosk)/*shpardhje*(Tosk), which means in Albanian: *Quercus frainetto*, the Italian

24 Ptolemy’s Geography tells us of a mountain range in Thrace with this name, and of a Thracian people/tribe whose endonym is an endonymic inflection of this name.

oak tree; cognate also to English “spar” meaning “rafter, beam, a bar of wood, pole (etc.)” and English “spear”. I derive Thracian Spart-/Sparat-/Sparad- from a root Spar/Sper=“hard, stiff, sharp, pointed, strong” (see PIE *(s)par, “beam, log”), and probably cognate to Etruscan Spur=“city”, which I derive from an earlier meaning “fortress/acropolis/peak”, meanings which derive from “pointed, projecting, stiff, hard”. PIE *sperH, “to kick” may be from “hard, stiff” (as seen with PIE *stewp, “to hit, push, strike” and those other examples) but more likely from a lost pre-PIE word for “foot” (see also PIE *sperH, “to trample”), with “foot” coming from “to plant in, to stand” (compare how *planta* in Latin means “a plant, seedling” etc. and also “sole of the foot”, both referring to planting onto/into the soil, sticking in and gripping, and Latin *planta* in all senses derives from Proto-Italic **plānktā* from **pl̥h₂nk/gteh₂* from **pleh₂k-*, **pleh₂g-/pel-* “to strike, beat, push, drive”, which I believe is cognate to PIE **pels/pelis*, “rock, cliff”, the root-meaning of “hard, stiff” in common between them; and I compare also PIE **perǵ-/porgʰos*, source of Proto-Slavic **pòrgъ*, “threshold, doorstep” and Lithuanian *pergas*, “fishing canoe”, both from “long beam, long post” and PIE **peh₂ǵ-* “to attach, fix, fasten” and PIE **peh₂k-* “to join, to attach; agreement, settlement”, both of which I derive from “hard, stiff, projecting, pointed” etc.) from “hard, stiff”: see also **spurq*=“track (as in a spoor, especially footprints)”, again most likely from a lost word for “foot”. I derive Ancient Greek Sparte/Sparta (Σπάρτη, Σπάρτα) from Spar= “firm, fortress”, cognate to Thracian Spartakus/Sparadokos/Sparadakus.

The PIE root **sper*, “to turn, twist” is the source of such words as σπάρτον (rope, cable) and σπεῖρα (rope, cord; knot or curl in wood, coils of a snake, etc.): I posit that the earlier meaning of this PIE **sper-* was “that which tightens”, from “tight, stiff”, cognate to **spar/sper*=“stiff, narrow, pointed; pole; strong”.

Ancient Greek κάρᾰβος (=a kind of beetle, probably the longhorn beetle; a kind of crustacean, probably a crayfish; a small boat) is from Karab=“hard, stiff, pointed, pole, projecting, tight”: the small boat meaning comes (as is usually the case) from “beams, posts” (and same etymology for καρᾰβιον), the beetle meaning from “hard” or the horn of the longhorn beetle; the crustacean/crayfish meaning from “tight pincer grip” most likely, and at the same time “hard (shell)”. Thracian Karabazmos, an epithet of the Horseman-Hero of Thracian mythology and religion, is probably from “Karab”=“spear” referring to the spear of that horseman, or from Karab=“strong, firm” or “sprouting” or maybe all those meanings. Ancient Greek γάρβρος “hornbeam” and γράβιον come from a root Garb-/Grab-/Karb-/Krab- cognate with Karab- described above and having the same semantic range (see my work on the Thracian Ezerovo inscription for more about this topic). Latin *carpinus* (=hornbeam oak) is thus a reference to both

“sprouting (the tree is known for its prolific shoots); pole” and “hard”. How much is Proto-Germanic **krabbô* from “to crawl (<claws), scratch, cut” (PIE **gerb^h-*) and how much is it from “tight hold of the pincers”? In any case, PIE **gerb^h-* “to scratch, cut” is cognate to the Grab/Garb/Krab/Kar(a)b root.

Ancient Greek *καρκίνος*, Sanskrit *karkaṭa* and Latin *cancer* (known to be from earlier **kark-*), are all from a Kark=“tight”, referring to how the crabs’ pincer grip is tight and strong (cf. PIE **kh₂er-*, “hard”): this etymology is indicated by Sanskrit *karkara* (“hard”) and by Ancient Greek *καρκίνωθρον/καρκίνηθρον* (=knotgrass/knotweed): here most likely Kark=“knot”, from “tight, strong, firm”: the knotgrass/knotweed is also a plant whose many roots are very firmly and strongly rooted in the ground. Romanian *țarc* (=corral, pen, enclosure), Albanian *thark/cark* (id.), Greek *τσάρκος* (id.) are from a root of identical semantics to Kark- described above, but in this case beginning with **k̑-* (see also PIE **k̑er*=“rope, string”, this root is from **k̑er*=“tight, firm, hard, pointed, sharp”: see also PIE **(s)ker-*, “to cut; sharp” which I posit is also from “tight, firm, hard, pointed, sharp” and thereby led to PIE **(s)ker-* “to bend, curve”, from the earlier meaning “rope, cord, string”, from “tight, firm”. Compare also the root Tark-/Targ- that I described earlier.

Similar to the Kinna=“stone, hard, firm, pointed, sharp” root is the Khn-/Kn-/Gn- root which I will now detail. Ancient Greek *χνόος*=“incrustation” I posit is from “to thicken, congeal”, from “thick, firm, hard, stiff, pointed; to project”. Ancient Greek *χνόη*=“axle-box, nave” is from “to fix, fasten” from “firm; to stick” which also owes something to “pointed; to thrust something pointed in like a nail so that it stays fast”. Ancient Greek *χναύω*=“to nibble” is from a lost *χνα-* word that meant “tooth” from “hard, peg, protuberance, projecting”; *χναῦμα*=“slice, tit-bit” is from *χνα-*=“sharp, pointed, hard, etc.”, leading to “to cut”. While *χναυρός*=“dainty” is probably from “of fine-taste”, and akin to *χναυστικός*=“one of a sweet tooth”, from **χνα-*=“tooth” < “hard, peg, protuberance, projecting”. In *Arachne/Arachnes* (“spider”), Ara=venomous (see my work on Arachne published elsewhere for details about that), and Chne/Khne might mean “fang, tooth”; otherwise Chne/Khne is just a suffix. In *Andrakhne*, Andra=“sweet” (from “pointed”, see my work on Andrakhne published elsewhere) while Khne may mean “plant” from “sprout, seedling; stem”: otherwise, -Khne in Andrakhne is just a suffix. Ancient Greek *πρόχνη* is either from Pro (forward)+ Khnu=“knee(s)”, not from **genu* but instead from a root beginning with Khn-=“hard, pointed, bony”); or otherwise Prokhnu is from Pro(forward)+Khnu (projecting)=“Projecting forward”, e.g. laying down prostrate with the arms stretched forward.

Knossos (from Minoan) probably meant “Fortress”, from “firm, strong” and from “hill, peak; pointed”. The Minoan Knossos is cognate to PIE **kneyd-*, “to scratch, scrape”, to Kinna=“stone, firm, hard, pointed”, etc. and to PIE **gned/*gnod*, “to bind”, which I posit is from earlier “tight, strong, stiff, pointed, sharp”. And I posit that PIE **ǵneh₃-* “to recognize, to know” is from earlier “to discern” in turn from “to separate” in turn from “to cut” (compare Latin *scio*, source of *scientia*) from **ǵneh₃-* =“sharp, pointed, hard, stiff, narrow, tight, strong, projecting”.

PIE **kenk*, source of Latin *cingō* +“I surround, circle, ring; I gird on, I crown or garland” I posited had the earlier meaning “tight, firm, strong, hard”. Variants of **kenk* were **keg* and **keng*.

4.

There was an ancient root **sel*=“stiff, hard, pole, beam, pointed, strong, sharp”, which is the source of Ancient Greek *σέλμᾱ* (=plank, logs, etc.) and *σελίς* (=crossbeam, rowing bench, etc.). The root may have had a variant **swel*. Latin *silva* (woods, forest) comes from this **sel* or **swel*, as does Ancient Greek *ὄλη* (“wood, trees, forest”). The Thracian or Ancient Greek name *Selys* thus most likely meant “strong, firm”. The Mycenaean Greek name *Hulaios* probably meant “strong, firm”, and so also the name *Hul(l)eus*. I posit that Ancient Greek *σέλινον* /*selinon* (celery) derives *Sel*=“stalk, stem, projecting up, pole”, not from “watery” as Ilija Casule posited years ago: the *sel*=“watery” etymology has no support in the Ancient Greek lexicon, which is quite suspicious. I posit that Proto-Germanic **swerdą* (“sword” and the source of English “sword”) derives from a PIE **swer*=“stiff, hard, strong, pointed, sharp”. Compare Proto-Germanic **sweruz*=“pole, pilar, column, neck”.

5.

There is a Latvian word *stāds* which means “plantlet, seedling, a young, usually not large plant, which was grown from planted seeds, cuttings, etc.; in other words, *stāds* refers (since sometime in the mid 19th century or so) to plants that were actually planted (e.g., in a garden) by someone, not to wild plants. Latvian *stāds* derives from PIE **steh₂-* “to stand (up)”.

Before the mid 19th century or so, Latvian *stāds* seems to have also meant “plant” in general, a “plant” of pretty much any kind, whether planted by a person or not: but in 1859 a word *augš* meaning “plant” was coined by Heinrihs Kavals,

from the same stem as the verb *augt* (=“to grow, to mature”), which was made into *augš*, a masculine first-declension noun (ending in *s*), and later popularized by Atis Kronvalds. Since then *augš* replaced in this sense of ‘plant’ the word *stāds*, now more restricted in its use (see details above). The alternative form *auģis*, proposed in the early 1860s by E. Dinsbergs, never became popular and was soon abandoned.

The main purpose of this discussion of Latvian *stāds* was to provide more background for my new etymology of Ancient Greek *σίδη/σίβδη/ ξίμβρα/σίδα/σιδέα* = “pomegranate”, which I posit derives from “seed (having many seeds)”, with *Sid*=“seed” deriving from *Sid*=“stiff, pointed, hard, sprouting/rising, stuck in firm/fast” as we see with Latvian *stāds* from PIE **steh₂*- “to stand (up)”. The etymology of “pomegranate” shows why “having many seeds” is likely for the pomegranate fruit/tree: “grenate” comes from Latin *granatus* meaning/implying “having many seeds”. The variant form *σίλβα* is probably a blend of the *Sid*- and *Sel/Selw*- root of Latin *Silva* (“forest, woods”).

It’s clear now that *Side* (pomegranate) does not refer to “red/blood” nor does Ancient Greek *σίδηρος*=“iron” refer to “red/blood”: I’m certain now that *σίδηρος*=“iron” derives from “hard, firm, stiff”. This is also indicated by the fact that *Side/Sibde* was the name of many cities in Ancient Greece and at least two in Anatolia: those would derive from “fortress; hard; stiff; strong; rising; elevated; hill”. The additional meaning “water-plant/water-lily” for the word *Side* most likely comes from “sprouting up; standing (in water)”. Latin *sidus*=“constellation; star” likely derives from “fixed, still”, from “firm, strong, hard”. And *sidus* also meant “meteorite”, which are often composed largely of iron: and maybe the “star” meaning derives from “iron” (in turn from “hard, firm, strong”), with many ancients believing that the stars were made of iron. PIE **sed-*, “to sit” most likely comes from “settled; still; established” from “firm, stiff” and “planted in”<“pointed”.

The variant form *ξίμβρα* for the pomegranate is cognate to Romanian *sâmbure* (=pit of a fruit; the central, core or essential part of something”) and to Albanian *thumbull* (“button”) and Albanian *thumb* (“sting, thorn, prick”), which are not from PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp”. They are in fact cognate to the ancient here-to-fore obscure European words *Dzomb/Zomb/Zob*=“European bison”: I posit that *Dzomb/Zomb/Zob*=“strong, firm”, from the wider set “strong, hard, firm, stiff, erect, pointed, sharp” and so the bison words also had a very phallic-male meaning.

The form *ξίμβρα* has a more distant but likely relationship to Ancient Greek *κυσήγη* (“pomegranate”) and Albanian *shegë* (=“pomegranate”), and so **K(V)seg-* likely meant “seed”, from “stiff, firm, stuck in fast”.

Proto-Germanic **silubrą*="silver" and Proto-Slavic **sьrebrò* ("silver") are likely altered from an earlier form that was a lot like Lithuanian *sidābras* ("silver"): I analyze *Sida-bras* as *Sida*=Metal (from *Sida*="hard, strong", cognate to *Sideros*="Iron") and *Bras/Brys/Bur/Bro*="white, bright" (this *Bras/Brys/Bur/Bro* could be cognate to English "Brass" and its Germanic cognates, all of obscure origin). Casule is probably wrong about the *sil-* in silver being from "watery": the *Sil/Sid* variation is probably due to *Sel*="hard, stiff, strong, firm" as described above. The form "Brys" is seen in Latgalian "Sudobrys"="silver". If the Brush of Sinkabrush (cinnabar) is cognate to this *Brys/Bras/Bur/Bro*, then *Sinka-Brush*="stone+red", with *Brush* from a set "red, bright, white" since all three of those meanings are associated with the brightness of dawn and the sun.

6.

It's clear to me that Latin *milvus* (=kite (the bird of prey), gurnard (the noisy fish) must come from a *Milw*="noisy, loud", likely cognate to PIE **melh₂-* "to grind, crush": but its unclear if the "noisy, loud" meaning came from "hard grinding stone" or if the "hard grinding stone" meaning came from "noisy, loud". PIE **meld^h-* "lightning" could come from the earlier meaning "thunder; loud; noisy": Finnish *melu*="noise, racket", as does Estonian *mõlu / mõlisema*. Latvian *mēle*="tongue" comes from "noisy", as does Lithuanian *melekėlis*="uvula". Alternatively, PIE **meld^h-* "lightning" comes from **mel(d^h)*="hard, pointed, sharp".

7.

As Furnée did many decades ago, I derive Ancient Greek *μύκης* ("mushroom; penis; stump of an olive tree; chape or cap at the end of a scabbard") from "prominence; projecting". This explains well the Ancient Greek toponym *Μυκῆναι* (Mycenae), which I derive from "hill, prominence; fortress" from "rising; stiff; hard; strong". And I interpret the common Thracian anthroponym element *Mouk-* as meaning "strong; hard" and having a very phallic connotation as well, all this explaining why that was such a popular Thracian name. Thracian *Mouk-* then is cognate to Ancient Greek *μύκης* and *Μυκῆναι*---and also to Romanian *muchie* (*mukie*)="top; edge; edge of a blade" and Italian *mucchio*, "heap, pile", and Italian *mugo* ("mountain pine") from Raetic **muku*, **mugu*.

8.

I posit that the Minoan/Linear A word *Po-to*/**Poto* (=big, grand”) is from a root *Po*=”to blow out, swell”, and so *Poto* is very similar to PIE **bewd-*, “to swell”: and Minoan *Poto* may even derive from Eteo-PIE **bewd-*, “to swell”, or from a variant **pewd-*. Compare Armenian *poytn/poyt/boytn*=”pot”, and compare also English “pot”, from Proto-Germanic **puttaz*, “pot”, and compare also Romanian *bot* (=bump, hump), Italian *bozza* (“bump”), Frankish *boce* (“knob”), and many more such words in many languages.

Minoan/Linear A *Ku-ro*/**Kuro* (=total, sum?) is likely from “top, summit”, just as the word “sum” derives from the earlier meaning “summit”; or *Kuro* could be from “mass, heap, pile”, as may be the origin of Latin *totus*, via the intermediary meaning “large group of people”. Either option²⁵ gives a similar type of root-word: *Ker/Kur/Kor*=”to rise; hard, stiff, erect; pointed; sharp”, and reminiscent of words in IE languages and Non-IE languages, such as Sumerian *Kur*=”mountain”. Among the likely IE correspondences are Ancient Greek *Κόρυθος*, where *Kor*=”peak, hill, elevation” and Ancient Greek *κόρυς*=”helmet”. I will have more in the next edition coming soon.

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25 Another option would be *Kuro* (“total, sum”) from “tie together”, in turn from *Kur*=”cord, rope”, from “that which tightens”, from *Kur*=”tight, stiff, hard, strong”.